

Chloromethylation of Some Biphenyl Derivatives

(Miss) B. Kanakalakshmi, K. P. Mathai, and Suresh Sethna

2, 2', 4, 4', 2, 3', 5, 5', & 2, 2', 0, 6'-Tetramethoxybiphenyls have been chloromethylated at the room temperature with excess of paraformaldehyde in dioxane or acetic acid medium. The structures of the chloromethyl derivatives have been established by either oxidation to the corresponding carboxylic acids or reduction to the corresponding methyl derivatives and by direct comparison of these products with those synthesised by unambiguous methods.

As a part of the systematic study of biphenyl derivatives, carried out in this laboratory, it was thought of interest to study chloromethylation of some tetramethoxybiphenyls. The present work deals with chloromethylation of 2, 2', 4, 4', 2, 2', 5, 5', and 2, 2', 6, 6'-tetramethoxybiphenyls.

Chloromethylation of 2, 2', 4, 4'-tetramethoxybiphenyl in dioxane provided a product, analysis of which agreed with di-(chloromethyl) derivative and which on oxidation with alkaline KMnO_4 in dioxane afforded 2, 2', 4, 4'-tetramethoxybiphenyl-5, 5'-dicarboxylic acid. This acid was synthesised for comparison as follows. 2, 4-Dimethoxy-5-iodoacetophenone, prepared according to Shah and Sethna¹, was oxidised with alkaline KMnO_4 to 2, 4-dimethoxy-5-iodobenzoic acid. This was esterified with dimethyl sulphate in acetone and subjected to Ullmann's reaction. Dimethyl 2, 2', 4, 4'-tetramethoxybiphenyl-5, 5'-dicarboxylate obtained was hydrolysed to the above acid with alkali.

2, 2', 5, 5'-Tetramethoxybiphenyl on chloromethylation in acetic acid furnished the 4, 4'-di-(chloromethyl) derivative which on oxidation with alkaline KMnO_4 provided the known 2, 2', 5, 5'-tetramethoxybiphenyl-4, 4'-dicarboxylic acid. Brockmann and Vorbruegg² obtained this acid by oxidation of 2, 2', 5, 5'-tetramethoxy-4, 4'-bis-(β -carboxypropionyl)biphenyl with sodium hypobromite. The present authors used alkaline KMnO_4 for this oxidation. The di-(chloromethyl) derivative, when subjected to reduction in dioxane with zinc and HCl , afforded 2, 2', 5, 5'-tetramethoxy-4, 4'-dimethylbiphenyl.

2, 2', 6, 6'-Tetramethoxybiphenyl on chloromethylation in acetic acid provided the 3, 3'-di-(chloromethyl) derivative which on reduction with zinc and HCl in dioxane yielded the 3, 3'-dimethylbiphenyl derivative, confirmed by direct comparison with the product obtained by the Ullmann reaction on 2, 4-dimethoxy-3-iodotoluene which in turn was prepared by the Sandmeyer reaction on 2, 6-dimethoxy-3-methylaniline³. Another product was isolated from the reaction mixture, analysis of which agreed with a tetra-(chloromethyl) derivative. 3, 3', 5, 5'-Tetra-(chloromethyl) structure has been tentatively assigned to the product as this appears to be the only possible structure.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 2676.

2. *Ber.*, 1862, 95, 610.

3. Mathai and Sethna, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 347.

The di-(chloromethyl) derivatives have been converted into the corresponding di-formyl derivatives by the Sommelet reaction and into the di-(acetoxyethyl) derivatives by sodium acetate and acetic anhydride.

EXPERIMENTAL

2, 2', 4, 4'-Tetramethoxy-5, 5'-di-(chloromethyl)biphenyl.—A mixture of paraformaldehyde (0.04M, 1.2 g.) and dioxane (10 ml) was saturated with dry HCl and 2, 2', 4, 4'-tetramethoxybiphenyl (0.01M, 2.74 g.) was added. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and the product separating was crystallised from xylene, m.p. 190°, yield 56%. (Found: C, 59.0; H, 5.2; Cl, 18.7. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4Cl_2$ requires C, 58.2; H, 5.4; Cl, 19.1%).

2, 2', 4, 4'-Tetramethoxybiphenyl-5, 5'-dicarboxylic Acid.—To the preceding biphenyl (0.5 g.), dissolved in dioxane (2 ml), $KMnO_4$ (2 g.) and 10% NaOH solution (10 ml) were added. The mixture after gentle reflux for 15 min. was filtered; the filtrate on acidification provided the 5,5'-dicarboxylic acid which on purification by bicarbonate treatment was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 255°. (Found: C, 59.5; H, 4.2. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 59.6; H, 4.6%). The same acid was prepared for comparison as follows.

2, 4-Dimethoxy-5-iodobenzoic Acid.—To 2,4-dimethoxy-5-iodoacetophenone¹ (2 g.) NaOH (20 ml, 20%) and $KMnO_4$ (6 g.) were added and the mixture was gently refluxed on a wire gauze for 1 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual was crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 210°. (Found: C, 34.9; H, 2.8; I, 41.2. $C_9H_8O_4I$ requires C, 35.1; H, 2.9; I, 41.2%).

Methyl 2, 4-Dimethoxy-5-iodobenzoate.—To the preceding acid (1 g.), dissolved in acetone (10 ml), dimethyl sulphate (1 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. on a steam bath. The reaction mixture was poured on water and the product separating was filtered. It was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 120°. (Found: C, 37.4; H, 3.8; I, 39.1. $C_{10}H_{11}O_4I$ requires C, 37.2; H, 3.4; I, 39.4%).

Dimethyl 2, 2', 4, 4'-Tetramethoxybiphenyl-5, 5'-dicarboxylate.—A mixture of the preceding ester (1 g.) and copper-bronze (2 g.) after heating in an oil bath at 225-30° for 2 hr. was extracted with benzene. The product obtained was recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 200°. (Found: C, 61.5; H, 5.7. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 61.5; H, 5.4%).

Hydrolysis.—The above ester (0.3 g.), dissolved in ethanol, was hydrolysed by refluxing with 10% NaOH solution (10 ml.) for 1 hr. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 255°. Mixed m.p. with 2, 2', 4, 4'-tetramethoxybiphenyl-5, 5'-dicarboxylic acid, described above, was not depressed.

2, 2', 4, 4'-Tetramethoxy-5, 5'-diformylbiphenyl.—The 5, 5'-di-(chloromethyl) derivative (1 g.) was refluxed with hexamine (6 g.) in chloroform (30 ml) on a steam bath for 2 hr. The complex separating was decomposed with dilute acetic acid by refluxing on a wire gauze for 1/2 hr. The product separating on cooling was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 245°. (Found: C, 65.4; H, 5.6. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5%). Apsimon *et al.*,² who have prepared this compound very recently by a different method, reported m.p. 238°.

¹ All melting points are uncorrected.

² *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 4157.

The *di*-(2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone), prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene, did not provide a definite m.p. It decomposed above 300°. (Found: N, 16.0. $C_{30}H_{16}O_{12}N_8$ requires N, 16.2%).

2, 2', 4, 4'-Tetramethoxy-5,5'-di-(acetoxymethyl)biphenyl, prepared by refluxing the 5,5'-di-(chloromethyl) derivative with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 6.5. $C_{28}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 63.2; H, 6.2%).

2, 2', 5, 5'-Tetramethoxy-4,4'-di-(chloromethyl)biphenyl.—To paraformaldehyde (0.04 *M*, 1.2 g.) in acetic acid (15 ml), saturated with dry HCl, 2, 2', 5, 5'-tetramethoxybiphenyl (0.01 *M*, 2.74 g.) was added. Next day the separated product was filtered and crystallised from xylene in colorless needles (78%), m.p. 102°. (Found: C, 58.1; H, 5.0; Cl, 18.9. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4Cl_2$ requires C, 58.2; H, 5.4; Cl, 19.1%).

2, 2', 5, 5'-Tetramethoxybiphenyl-4, 4'-dicarboxylic Acid.—To the preceding biphenyl (0.5 g.) NaOH (10 ml, 10%) and $KMnO_4$ (2 g.) were added; the reaction mixture after gentle heating over a wire gauze for 1 hr. was filtered. The filtrate on acidification provided the 4, 4'-dicarboxylic acid which on being purified as usual was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 255°. (Found: C, 59.2; H, 4.3. $C_{18}H_{10}O_8$ requires C, 59.0; H, 4.6%).

The same acid was prepared for comparison as follows. 2, 2', 5, 5'-tetramethoxy-4,4'-bis-(β -carboxypropionyl)biphenyl² (0.5 g.) was refluxed with $KMnO_4$ (4 g.) and NaOH (20 ml, 10%) for 1/2 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual was crystallised from ethanol. Mixed m.p. with the acid, described above, was not depressed. Brockmann and Vorbreggen³ have reported m.p. 244-46°.

2, 2', 5, 5'-Tetramethoxy-4, 4'-dimethylbiphenyl.—To the preceding biphenyl (0.5 g.), dissolved in dioxane, zinc dust (2 g.) was added, followed by HCl (conc., 5 ml; portionwise). The reaction mixture after refluxing for 1 hr. on a steam bath was filtered; the filtrate on dilution provided the dimethyl derivative. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 71.8; H, 7.2. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.3%). Fichter⁴, who prepared the same compound by a different method, reported m.p. 135°.

2, 2', 5, 5'-Tetramethoxy-4,4'-diformylbiphenyl.—The 4,4'-di-(chloromethyl) derivative (1 g.) was refluxed with hexamine (6 g.) in chloroform (30 ml) for 2 hr. and the complex obtained was decomposed with dilute acetic acid by heating gently on a wire gauze for 2 hr. The product separating on cooling was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 237°. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 5.2. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5%).

The *di*-(2,4-DNP) was prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. >325°. (Found: N, 16.5. $C_{30}H_{14}O_{12}N_8$ requires N, 16.2%).

2, 2', 5, 5'-Tetramethoxy-4,4'-di-(acetoxymethyl)biphenyl, prepared from the 4,4'-di-(chloromethyl) derivative by refluxing with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, was crystallised from benzene in colorless needles, m.p. 160-70°. (Found: C, 63.4; H, 6.1. $C_{28}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 63.2; H, 6.2%).

2, 2', 6, 6'-Tetramethoxy-3,3'-di-(chloromethyl)biphenyl.—Dry HCl gas was passed through excess of paraformaldehyde (0.04 *M*, 1.2 g.) in acetic acid (15 ml) at the room tem-

perature till the paraformaldehyde dissolved and 2,2',6,6'-tetramethoxybiphenyl (0.01M, 2.74 g.) was then added. The product separating on keeping overnight was crystallised from benzene in colorless cubes (87%), m.p. 200°. (decomp.). (Found: C, 58.4; H, 5.7; Cl, 19.0. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4Cl_2$ requires C, 58.2; H, 5.4; Cl, 19.1%).

2, 2', 6, 6'-*Tetramethoxy-3,3',5,5'-tetra-(chloromethyl)biphenyl*.—After removing the 3,3'-di-(chloromethyl) derivative from the above reaction mixture, the filtrate was poured on water and the separated product was crystallised from light petroleum, m.p. 110°, yield 15%. (Found: C, 51.0; H, 4.3; Cl, 30.0. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4Cl_4$ requires C, 51.3; H, 4.7; Cl, 30.3%).

2,2',6,6'-*Tetramethoxy-3,3' dimethylbiphenyl*.—To 2,2', 6,6'-Tetramethoxy-3,3'-di-(chloromethyl)biphenyl (0.5 g.), dissolved in dioxane, zinc dust (2 g.) was added, followed by HCl (conc.) in instalments. The mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 1 hr, filtered, and the filtrate on dilution provided the dimethyl derivative. It was crystallised from light petroleum in cubes, m.p. 101°. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 7.5. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.9%). The same dimethyl derivative was prepared by another method for comparison as follows.

2,4-Dimethoxy-3-iodotoluene.—2,6-Dimethoxy-3-methylaniline³ (2 g.), dissolved in HCl (1:1, 15 ml) was cooled below 5° and to it sodium nitrite solution (1g. in 5 ml water) was added portionwise. The reaction mixture was kept for 1/2 hr. below 5°. Potassium iodide (4 g. in 10 ml water) was added to it and the mixture kept for 1 hr. at the room temperature. It was heated on a steam bath for 1 hr. and the product separating was filtered and crystallised from light petroleum, m.p. 86°. (Found: C, 38.7; H, 3.7; I, 45.6. $C_9H_{11}O_2I$ requires C, 38.3; H, 4.0; I, 45.7%).

Ullmann Reaction.—The above iodo derivative (1 g.), mixed with copper bronze (2 g.), was heated in an oil-bath at 225-35° for 2 hr. The reaction product was extracted with benzene and crystallised from light petroleum. Mixed m.p. with 2,2',6,6'-tetramethoxy-3,3'-dimethylbiphenyl, described above, was not depressed.

2, 2',6,6'-*Tetramethoxy-3, 3'-diformylbiphenyl*.—To the 3,3'-di-(chloromethyl) derivative (1 g.), dissolved in chloroform (30 ml), hexamine (6 g.) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. The separated complex was filtered and refluxed with dilute acetic acid for 2 hr. On cooling, the formyl derivative separating was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 152°. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 5.4. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5%).

The di-(2,4-DNP), prepared as usual, was crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. 290-91°. (Found: N, 15.9. $C_{30}H_{24}O_{12}N_8$ requires N, 16.2%.)

2, 2', 6, 6'-*Tetramethoxy-3,3'-di-(acetoxyethyl)biphenyl* was prepared by refluxing the 3,3'-di-(chloromethyl) derivative with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. It was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 114°. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 6.1. $C_{22}H_{26}O_8$ requires C, 63.2; H, 6.2%).

One of the authors (B.K.) thanks the University Grants Commission for the award of a research scholarship.